

THE HISTORY OF ARABIC BORROWINGS IN ENGLISH AND THEIR INFLUENCE OVER ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT: *In the given article there were given a theoretical understanding about the history of Arabic borrowings in English and presented further information about the borrowing process and its influence on English. In English vocabulary there are many words which were derived from Arabic like other European language. Although Arabic and English are not from the same family and different from the point of areal typology, Arabic influenced English via other world languages like French, Spanish, etc. It is evident that the main way in which Arabic borrowings entered English is that there was a political reason that existed due to Islamic Caliphate that had significant influence over the countries they ruled and English was in contact with those languages though it was not conquered by Arabs.*

Keywords: *borrowing, loans, Arabic words, Arabic terms, English vocabulary, Modern English.*

ANNOTATSIYA: *Maqolada ingliz tilida mavjud arab tilidan kirib kelgan so`zlarning ingliz tiliga kirib kelish tarixi haqida nazariy ma`lumotlar berilgan va bu jarayonning ingliz tiliga ta`siri haqida ma`lumotlar berilgan. Boshqa tillardagi kabi ingliz tilidan ham arab tilidn kirib kelgan so`zlar ko`p. Til oilasi va areal tipologiya jihatidan arab va ingliz tili bir xil bo`lmasada, arab tili fransuz, ispan tillari kabi chet tillari orqali ingliz tiliga ta`sir ko`rsatgan. Ingliz tiliga arab so`zlarinong kirib kelishining asosiy yo`li Islom xalifaligi ta`sirida bo`lgan mamlakat tillari bilan ingliz tilini aloqada bo`lganligidir.*

Kalit so`zlar: *o`zlashma so`zlar, arabcha so`zlar, arabcha terminlar, ingliz tili lug`ati, zamonaviy ingliz tili.*

INTRODUCTION Hundreds of terms from the Arabic language have entered the English language through various ways throughout history. However, due to linguistic and phonetic restrictions, some modifications in the pronunciation of loan terms have occurred as adoption and assimilation progressed. In certain circumstances, the difference in pronunciation is so

different that it is difficult to distinguish the original terms. Many words were borrowed from Arabic when Arabic influence was its paramount stage and the realm of Islam was far-spread over the world. During the eighth century the Iberian Peninsula was occupied by Arabs, as a result their culture, language integrated with the native's. over the next few centuries in this Peninsula Christian forces took control and Arabic and Christian culture and language started to merge together and influenced each other. In this way English also was influenced by Arabic despite the fact that Arabs did not occupy the British Isles.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS Linguists have studied the Arabic loaning process in English by dividing them into periods and what changes occurred in the vocabulary system of English during that time. The division follows as:

The early loaning According to Wilson [2001], Arabic had supplanted Latin as the main language in North Africa by the ninth century, and Arabic culture had fully expanded over Spain by the eleventh and twelfth centuries. In reality, John, Bishop of Seville, began translating the Bible into Arabic as early as 724.

According to Serjeantson [1935], the first English word borrowed from Arabic is 'mancus,' which comes from the Arabic word 'manqsh,' which meaning 'to sculpt, engrave, inscribe,' and was typically used in the context of coinage to mean 'struck.' The word 'mancus' spread swiftly in Italy after its initial mention in the 770s. By the 780s, they had made it to England. Pope Innocent III wrote a letter to King Coenwulf of the Mercians in 798. Leo III alludes to King Offa's commitment to send 365 mancuses to Rome every year in 786. On the other hand, according to Breeze [1991], ealfara is the earliest known Arabic loanword to English. The word "pack-horse" refers to a horse that is employed to convey goods. It's derived from the Hispano-Arabic term sal-fara, which literally means "horse." It first appears in "Alexander's letter to Aristotle" in the 11th century, and an Old French term (as auferan) with a similar meaning. "It is possible that French [borrowing through Arabic] was the direct source of the phrase in English," Serjeantson (1935, p. 214) says. Breeze (1991) disagrees, saying that Alexander's Letter to Aristotle's translator may have been a woman.

Middle English "the age of loaning" English speakers came into contact with the prominent intellectual centers of the Arab world during the Middle and Renaissance Ages. This interaction resulted in a flood of Arabic borrowings into English, mainly in the domains of chemistry, medicine, philosophy, mathematics, astronomy, optics, physics, botany, literature, religion (particularly Islam), music, warfare, shipping, trade, architecture, governance, and sovereignty [Daher, 2003].

Chaucer's use of Arabic words According to Wilson [2001], Chaucer was the first to utilize twenty-four new Arabic loanwords (mainly through French).

No other Medieval or Renaissance British author (including Shakespeare) used an Arabic loanword for the first time, according to Cannon's Historical Dictionary. The following are examples of Arabic loanwords first reported in Chaucer's works:

- * (of astronomy) Almagest, almanac, almucantar, almury, Alnath, nadir
- * (of chemistry) alkali, azimuth, borax, tartar, amalgam (as a verb)
- * (of clothing) satin, gipon
- * (of the military) lancegay, jupon
- * (of games) fers, checkmate
- * (miscellaneous) Damask, Sarsenish, fen, ribibe, carrack, dulcarnon

The majority of Arabic terms entered the English language in medieval times through French. According to the Oxford English Dictionary, the term 'admiral' first appears in 1205, most likely borrowed from the Old French 'amiral' or directly from Arabic *amir al*, which means 'commander of,' as noted by Langacker [1967]. Similarly, the term "lute" (13th century) is derived from the Old French "lut," which is derived from the Arabic "al-ud" (the oud). Because of this unintentional adoption of the Arabic article, the oud becomes a 'lute' [Oxford Etymology Dictionary].

Early modern English According to Smith [2007], English commercial seafarers were exploring the globe beyond Europe's borders by the time of Elizabeth I (1533–1603), bringing back rich and exotic artifacts, resources, and cultures from the Middle East and beyond. Many of the Arabic terms that travelers carried back with them at the period reflect a pleasant, if not affluent, way of life. All of the ingredients in sugar, syrup, julep, sherbet, and marzipan are Arabic in origin.

Modern English (1776–present) European dominance over Arabic-speaking regions began in the eighteenth century. As a result, the borrowing trend has shifted: Nonetheless, English adopted a few Arabic terms, including Bedouin, gazelle, giraffe, hashish, minaret, mosque, sultan, vizier, bazaar, caravan, and so on.

CONCLUSION It is obvious that Arabic had a great influence over world languages including English. As have been discussed above Arabic had a great effect on other world languages due to Islamic Renaissance in the medieval centuries. So many words from Arabic started to being adapted to the languages that were under the influence of Islamic Caliphate. Different tribes and other parts of the world accepted Islam as their religion and Caliphates ruled the countries and tried to become a part of the countries they had influence. As a consequence, many words, terms, phrases in Arabic spread into many languages across the globe.

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